

DEVELOPING A QUALITATIVE RESEARCH MANUSCRIPT BASED ON SYSTEMATIC CURRICULUM AND INSTRUCTIONAL DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract:

The aim of this study is to present a learning package which provides the necessary knowledge and attitudinal information, and practice opportunities based on SCID (Systematic Curriculum and Instructional Development) for the task of developing a qualitative research manuscript correctly. This learning package is organized based on three enabling objectives: practice writing methodology of qualitative data, practice analyzing qualitative data and practice discussing and concluding results. To achieve those three enabling objectives learner should follow the steps of learning activities consisting of information sheet with samples of author's qualitative research articles published in various journals, self-check model questions and answers, and practice exercises in addition to final performance test and standards.

Keywords: systematic curriculum and instructional development, qualitative research

1. Introduction

Developing a qualitative research manuscript is a part of building a component academic staff in social sciences. This guide will provide you the general knowledge and skills needed to develop a qualitative research manuscript for your academic position. As part of the academic staff, it is important to understand and to complete a project with a genuine research at an advanced level both individually and as a member of a research team. Generating new knowledge in the field of qualitative research will aid your growth and competence among academic staff for prospective promotion in your career. This guide will help you become successful in those efforts.

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1.1 Performance Objective

Given qualitative data, write a qualitative manuscript. The finished job must meet all criteria on Performance Test on 5 and 5.1.

1.2 Enabling Objectives

1. Practice writing methodology of qualitative data.
2. Practice analyzing qualitative data.
3. Practice discussing and concluding results

1.3 Prerequisites

- Master / PhD degree in the related field;
- Knowledge of using ICT (word, excel, adobe), using Data Analysis Software(quantitative or qualitative NVIVO, SPPSS) Analytical thinking, critical thinking;
- Knowledge of philosophy of social sciences.

2. Writing Methodology of Qualitative Data

As seen in Table 1: Learning Experience #1, you should follow the steps of learning activities by taking care of special instructions in practice writing methodology of qualitative data.

Table 1: Learning Experience #1

Enabling Objective #1: Practice writing methodology of qualitative Data	
Learning Activities	Special Instructions
Read the Information Sheet titled "Writing Methodology of Qualitative Data" on 2.1, 2.2,2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 2.6, 2.7, 2.8, 2.9, 2.10,2.11	
Watch the Qualitative data analysis video and identify the important messages to convey about your university when developing a qualitative research manuscript.	https://www.qsrinternational.com/nvivo/nvivo-12-tutorial-windows/00-let-s-get-started
Discuss with the instructor expert in qualitative research at your faculty the methods he or she uses to develop a qualitative research manuscript. What would you have to do differently?	Ask your mentor to suggest a co-researcher who can observe and help you with your practice sessions and the Practice Checklist.
Demonstrate your knowledge of developing a qualitative research manuscript by completing the Self-Check on 2.12.	
Check your answers against the Self-Check Model Answers on 2.13.	
Practice writing methodology of qualitative data while the academic staff expert in qualitative research observes and offers help as needed. Ask	

the academic staff expert in qualitative research to use the checklist titled "Practice Writing the Methodology of Qualitative Data" on 2.14 to assess your progress.

2.1 Determining the Title of the Manuscript

You should decide what the correct and comprehensive title for the research is by taking care of your research aim so that the title reflects the whole manuscript and makes a sense.

For example if you do a qualitative research to understand the kinds of stressors originating from academic work setting, the influences of those kinds of stressors on academic staff and to know how they overcame stress at work setting, the title of your manuscript can be written as 'Job Stressors And Their Effects On Academic Staff: A Case Study`.

2.2 Writing the Abstract and Key Words

You should decide what and how many words of abstract and key words to use to reflect the entire research (aim, methodology, findings and implications) based on database searching engine in the research topic you chose so that abstract and key words should reflect the whole manuscript and makes a sense.

For example for the abstract and key words of the qualitative research called Job Stressors and Their Effects on Academic Staff: A Case Study (Gunbayi, 2014) to understand the kinds of stressors originating from academic work setting, the influences of those kinds of stressors on academic staff and to know how they overcame stress at work setting can be as following:

"The purpose of this study was to understand the kinds of stressors originating from academic work setting, the influences of those kinds of stressors on academic staff and to know how they overcame stress at work setting. A non-probability sample was used...A qualitative approach with a multiple case study with embedded units was selected for this study. Semi-structured individual and focus group interviews, participant observations and document analysis of staff's weekly schedules were used to collect data. Findings showed that there were intensive and various kinds of stress originating from stressors in academic setting and the effects of stress might be either negative or positive. Thus, the outcome of the research addresses important implications for the professional work life of academic staff in understanding how stress influences academic staff's performance negatively and positively, identifying where negative and positive stress exist in academic setting and knowing how to overcome stressors originating from academic settings. Key Words: Stressors, academic staff, teacher training college, case study."

(Gunbayi, 2014: 58)

2.3 Reviewing the Literature

You should decide what philosophies, paradigms, (Gunbayi and Sorm, 2018) reference books, articles, dissertations to review and what scientific search engines to use. Review data bases of research field related to your research aim carefully to contribute the research field and to support your research aim and research questions and enable readers to understand why you do this research and what contribution it will make to research field.

2.4 Explaining the Research Aim and Write Research Questions

You should decide what and how many research questions to write to reach the aim of the research by reviewing the literature related to research topic so that the data you collect and your findings should answer the research questions and keep you up with the research aim.

For example for the research aim and research questions to understand the kinds of stressors originating from academic work setting, the influences of those kinds of stressors on academic staff and to know how they overcame stress at work setting can be as follows:

“The purpose of this study was to understand what it was like to work amidst stressors originating from work setting, to understand the influences of those kinds of stressors on academic staff and to know the way they overcome stressors at work setting. Thus, this study examined:

1. *“How does academic staff define stress?”*
2. *What are academic staff’s perceptions on stressors originating from work setting?*
3. *How do stressors affect academic staff?*
4. *How does academic staff overcome stress as a result of stressors in academic setting?”*

(Gunbayi, 2014:59)

2.5 Explaining What Qualitative Design Chosen

You should decide which qualitative design to choose and why based on experience and reference book suggestions of qualitative research methods so that the design you choose should comply with your research aim and you may mislead readers to do study.

For example for explanation of what qualitative design were chosen to understand the kinds of stressors originating from academic work setting, the influences of those kinds of stressors on academic staff and to know how they overcame stress at work setting can be as following:

“A qualitative approach was selected for this study because this research was more concerned with understanding individuals’ perceptions of the world and seeking insights rather than statistical analysis (Silverman, 2005). Because investigation of academic staff’s experiences related to stressors originating formal academic setting, college

campuses were viewed as an instrumental case study. In qualitative research design, the case study method allows investigators to retain the holistic and meaningful characteristics of real-life events—such as individual life cycles, small group behavior, organizational and managerial processes, school performance, and interpersonal relations in real contexts (Cohen et al, 2007; Yin, 2012). Thus, the focus of this study was influences of job stressors on academic staff in college setting and their perceptions by informants. As this study was carried out in....., a qualitative approach with a multiple case study with embedded units was selected for this study. In a multiple case study with embedded units different sub-units may be involved in each of the different cases, and a range of instruments used for each sub-unit, and each is kept separate to each case (Yin, 2012)."

(Gunbayi, 2014)

2.6 Explaining Sampling Methods and Techniques

You should decide which sampling methods and techniques to choose and why based on experience and reference book suggestions of sampling strategy in a research so that the data you collected from the sampling should support your aim and may not mislead you.

For example for sampling methods and techniques chosen to understand the kinds of stressors originating from academic work setting, the influences of those kinds of stressors on academic staff and to know how they overcame stress at work setting can be as following:

"This study was conducted from through withvolunteer participants. A non-probability sample technique based on purposive sampling method was used because 'the sample derives from the researcher targeting a particular group, in the full knowledge that it does not represent the wider population, it simply represent itself. This is frequently the in small scale research, for example, as with one or two schools, two or three groups of students, or a particular group of teachers, where no attempt to generalize is desired; this is frequently the case for qualitative researches (Cohen, Manion & Morrison, 2007) such as action ethnographic or case."

(Gunbayi, 2014: 59).

2.7 Explaining Data Collection Methods and Techniques

You should explain which sampling methods and techniques to choose and why based on experience and reference book suggestions of qualitative research methods so that the data you collected from the sampling do should support your aim.

For example for explaining data collection methods and techniques to understand the kinds of stressors originating from academic work setting, the influences of those kinds of stressors on academic staff and to know how they overcame stress at work setting can be as following:

“In order to investigate academic staff’ perceptions on stressors originating from work setting, to understand the influences of those kinds of stressors on academic staff and to know how they overcame stress at work setting, semi-structured individual and focus group interviews were used because it would provide an in depth exploration of the topic, it would allow me the flexibility, for example, to change the order of questions, simplify the questions and to probe the interviews (Cohen et al, 2007). Data were collected from ... through ... This included about 45 minute recorded individual interviews and about one and half focus group interview with the informants with initial interview questions. I used face-to-face interviews. I recorded informants’ experiences, thoughts and feelings in a taped diary. Additionally participant observations in classes and staff rooms and document analysis based on academic staff’s weekly agenda were used to collect data.”

(Gunbayi, 2014: 60)

2.8 Explaining Reliability and Validity of the Research

You should explain what to do to support reliability and validity of the research by doing a pilot study for reliability and validity of the study to guarantee high reliability and validity of the research.

For example for reliability and validity of the research to understand the kinds of stressors originating from academic work setting, the influences of those kinds of stressors on academic staff and to know how they overcame stress at work setting can be as following:

“In order to ensure reliability and validity of the study, some steps were followed: (i) data were collected from various sources such as interviews (individual and focus group), participant observations and documents in terms of triangulation (ii) data were used as direct quotations from the interviews without making any comments on them, (iii) a purposive sampling method based on voluntarism was used in order to get opinions and experiences of academic staff in (iv) data were coded by two independent researchers and Cohen’s kappa coefficient were calculated to determine inter-rater reliability of themes coded -0.814 perfect agreement- for inner reliability (Landis & Koach, 1977) and (v) records of interviews, documents and participant observations were kept for outer reliability”

(Gunbayi, 2014: 61)

2.9 Reporting Ethical Process

You keep up with what steps to follow to conform to the ethics committee of social science researches according to ethical regulations form of the ethical committee and get ethical approval before doing your research. For example for ethical process of the research to understand the kinds of stressors originating from academic work setting, the influences of those kinds of stressors on academic staff and to know how they overcame stress at work setting can be as following:

“Participants were briefed about the research aims, kept informed at all stages and be offered anonymity. A consent form was signed between researcher and each participant about the use of the data in terms of how its analysis would be reported and disseminated. It was also tried to be careful not to impose researcher’s belief on others and researcher’s beliefs were secondary and the participants thinking be what was required.”

Gunbayi, 2014: 61)

2.10 Tools, Equipment, Supplies, and Materials

The following tools, equipment, supplies, and materials are needed to developing a qualitative research manuscript

Table 2: Tools, Equipment, Supplies, and Materials for Enabling Objective #1

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Computers, • Laptop Software • Textbooks, • Articles, • Databases in related field, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quantitative analysis software (SPSS, Lisrel), • Plagiarism Detection Software • Microsoft Office • Internet • Printer/scanner/fax
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2.11 Worker Behaviors

Academician behaviors play a key role in developing a qualitative research manuscript. The behaviors important to your success in completing this task are:

Table 3: Worker Behaviors for Enabling Objective #1

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Good Listener • Assertive • Flexible • Professional • Adaptable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Punctual • Ethical Reliable • Objective • Safety-oriented • Goal driven
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2.12 Self Check

Directions: Check your knowledge of developing a qualitative research manuscript by responding to the following questions. For True/False questions, circle “True” if the statement is correct and circle “False” if the statement is incorrect. For multiple choice questions, select the response that is most correct. For short answer questions, write a brief response to the question. Check your answers with those on the Self-Check Model Answers page that follows.

Table 4: Self Check for Enabling Objective #1

1. The title of the manuscript does not necessarily reflects the whole manuscript and make a sense.

True
False

2. Key words reflect the whole manuscript and make a sense.

True

False

3. Literature review supports your research aim and research questions and Readers can understand why you do this research and what contribution you do to research field.

True
False

4. The data you collect and your findings answer the research questions and keep you with the research aim

True
False

5. The design you choose does not necessarily complies with your research aim.

True
False

6. The sampling method which supports a qualitative research can be (choose more than one):

- a. Probability sampling
 - b. Non-probability sampling
 - c. Purposive sampling
 - d. Random sampling
-

7. Identify the types of validity and reliability in a qualitative research
-

8. Why is research ethics important? Give your reasons
-

2.13 Self-Check Model Answers

Directions: Compare your answers to the Self-Check with the Model Answers provided below.

Table 5: Self-Check Model Answers for Enabling Objective #1

1. False The title of the manuscript must necessarily reflect the whole manuscript otherwise it does not make a sense.
-

2. True
-

3. True
-
-

4.	True	
5.	False	You should choose your qualitative design according to research aim e.g. if you research what is here and now, you should case study
6.	b. c.	Non-probability sampling Purposive sampling
7.	Inner Validity Outer Validity Inner Reliability Outer Reliability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Triangulation. • A purposive sampling method based on voluntarism to get opinions and experiences. • Data coded by two independent researchers and Cohen's kappa coefficient calculated to determine inter-rater reliability of themes. • All data collected should be kept to prove on demand.
8.	Model Answer	If you do not keep up with ethical procedures in the research, your research become meaningless and you can get some penalties by the ethical committee in your institution and as a scientist you have a bad reputation.

2.14 Practice Exercise

You should follow directions below for Practice Exercise for Enabling Objective #1:

- Review your ability to write the methodology of qualitative data using the following checklist as a guide.
- Discuss with your co-researcher the fundamentals of this task.
- Practice each stage of writing methodology of qualitative data.
- Ask your co-researcher to use the checklist to evaluate your ability to perform this task.

Table 6: Practice Exercise for Enabling Objective #1

Writing The Methodology Of Qualitative Data

Actions	Level of Performance		
	Yes	With Help	No
When writing the methodology of qualitative data, the learner...			
1. Determined title appropriate with the manuscript.			
2. Completed abstract that reflected the content accurately			
3. Defined the research problem clearly, tied to the relevant literature, up to date, completed with literature review with appropriate references			
4. Determined research questions appropriate with research aim			

-
-
5. Selected qualitative design consistent with the aim of the research

 6. Explained sampling methodology, chose correct sampling size

 7. Explained data collection method through semi-structured individual and focus group interviews, organized observations and collected documents

 8. Followed steps to ensure reliability and validity of the study

Level of Performance: When you are finished with this Practice Exercise, you should be able to comfortably discuss and perform any of the actions included in it. Your ratings on the checklist for this Practice Exercise should be Yes for all items. If you received With Help or No ratings for any items, review your performance with your mentor.

3. Analyzing Qualitative Data

As seen in Table 7: Learning Experience #2, you should follow the steps of learning activities by taking care of special instructions in practice analyzing qualitative data.

Table 7: Learning Experience #2

Enabling Objective #2: Practice Analyzing Qualitative Data	
Learning Activities	Special Instructions
Read the Information Sheet titled “Analyzing Qualitative Data” on 3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6 and 3.7	
Watch the Qualitative data analysis video and identify the important messages to convey about your academic position at university when developing a qualitative research manuscript.	https://www.qsrinternational.com/nvivo/nvivo-12-tutorial-windows/00-let-s-get-started
Discuss with the instructor expert in qualitative research at your faculty the methods he or she uses to analyze qualitative data. What would you have to do differently?	Ask your mentor to suggest a co-researcher who can observe and help you with your practice sessions and the Practice Checklist.
Demonstrate your knowledge of analyzing qualitative data by completing the Self-Check on 3.8.	
Check your answers against the Self-Check Model Answers on 3.9.	
Practice Analyzing Qualitative Data while the academic staff expert in qualitative research observes and offers help as needed. Ask the academic staff expert in qualitative research to use the checklist titled “Practice Analyzing Qualitative Data “on 3.10 to assess your progress.	

3.1 Organizing Data Categorically and Chronically

Data analysis should with repeated readings of interview transcripts from conversations with participants. The purpose was to determine the essence of the phenomenon and structures of experiences of participants on the topic research. During data analysis, the data should be organized categorically and chronically, reviewed repeatedly and continually coded. Interview transcripts were regularly reviewed. In addition, data analysis process can be aided by the use of a qualitative data analysis computer program called NVIVO. However, remember that these kinds of computer programs do not actually perform the analysis but facilitate and assist it. That is NVIVO 9.2 does not perform the analysis but only supports the researcher doing the analysis by organizing data and recodes and nodes etc.

For example in the article called The Opinions Of The Principals And Teachers Working In Vocational Training High School And Vocational High School On Leonardo Da Vinci Project: A Case Study (Gunbayi and Yassıkaya, 2011) the aim to classify the opinions of the principals and teachers working in Vocational Training High school and Vocational High School on Leonardo Da Vinci Project as the reasons for joining this Project, the preparations before the Project and the benefits of the Project, The perceptions and frequency analysis of two principals and six teachers related to why they participated in Leonardo da Vinci Project can be seen in Figure1 and Table 8.

Figure 1: The reasons for participating in Leonardo Da Vinci Project

Source: Gunbayi and Yassıkaya (2011)

Table 8: The reasons for participating in Leonardo Da Vinci Project

The reasons for participating	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	f
Seeing European Union countries	√	√						√	3
Willingness for participating in the project							√	√	2
Having a part in a project before			√			√			2
Observing vocational education in a European Union country	√			√					2
Learning about education system of a different country		√	√						2
Transferring best examples in Europe to Turkey	√								1

Having information about historical and touristy places	√	1
Expanding one's horizon	√	1

Source: Gunbayi and Yassıkaya (2011)

3.2 Discussing Findings of Data Collected via Individual Interviews

You should first transcript your individual interviews, review repeatedly and continually code by using qualitative software NVIVO as follows:

Figure 2: Coding by using qualitative software NVIVO

Source: QSR (2018)

Then as seen in Table 8 you can show frequency analysis for the opinions of the participants on the reasons for seeing European Union countries and under this table you can analyze the data descriptively as follows:

As seen in Table 8, 3/8 of participants participated in Leonardo Da Vinci Project as they wanted to see European Union countries and they explained their reasons as follows:

"<Internals \ \interviews \ \A> -

I, as a principal of this school, desired some of my colleagues to visit and see European countries.

<Internals \ \interviews \ \B>

visit and see Germany.

<Internals \ \interviews \ \H> -

we believe that it would be beneficial to visit and see European countries."

(Gunbayi and Yassıkaya, 2011: 20-21)

When completed analyzing data descriptively, now it is time for you do content analysis. Content analyses enable you to analyze the data in depth by explaining the relation between independent variable and dependent variable.

For example in the research done to classify the opinions of the principals and teachers working in Vocational Training High school and Vocational High School on Leonardo Da Vinci Project as the reasons of joining this Project, content analysis can be done as follows:

Table 9: Row Percentage of the Reasons for Participating
in Leonardo Da Vinci Project for Positions

The reasons for participating in Leonardo Da Vinci Project	Principal	Teacher
1 : Seeing European Union countries	62,86%	37,14%
2 : Willingness for participating in the project	0%	100%
3 : Having a part in a project before	0%	100%
4 : Observing vocational education in a European Union country	53,85%	46,15%
5 : Learning about education system of a different country	44,12%	55,88%
6 : Transferring best examples in Europe to Turkey	100%	0%
7 : Having information about historical and touristy places	0%	100%
8 : Expanding one's horizon	100%	0%

Source: Gunbayi and Yassıkaya (2011)

Figure 3: Matrix Coding Query for the Reasons for Participating
in Leonardo Da Vinci Project for Positions

Source: Gunbayi and Yassıkaya (2011)

“When the reasons why principals participated in Leonardo Da Vinci project are analyzed in general, the principals in terms of school effectiveness and efficiency wanted the teachers to see European countries, to observe vocational education in European Union countries, to transfer best examples in Europe to Turkey and to expand their horizons and on the other hand, when the reasons why teachers participated in Leonardo Da Vinci project are analyzed in general, in consistent with the views of the principals

the teachers wanted to know about European countries, to observe education system of a different country and to be helpful for the project."

(Gunbayi, 2011:22).

3.3 Discussing Findings of Data Collected Via Focus Group Interviews

When you discuss data of focus group interviews, you should first transcript your focus group interviews, review repeatedly and continually code as you do in discussing findings of data collected via individual interviews.

For example, focus group analysis for the study done to understand the kinds of stressors originating from academic work setting, the influences of those kinds of stressors on academic staff and to know how they overcame stress at work setting can be as following:

With participants PDA, PDB, PDC and PDD in addition to individual interviews, a focus group interview was also done at at ... on The focus group interview was done in PDC's own classroom in ...with the same questions except metaphor question: definition of stress, the stressors at work, the effect of stressors and the ways to cope with stress. All participants used nearly the same definition for the word stress. They all agreed on the definition of stress as "*feeling of not being able to carry out her duties and responsibilities on time and sufficiently due to time pressure, deadline and combinations of lots of work at the same time*" (Gunbayi, 2014: 66).

3.4 Discussing Findings of Data Collected via Observations

When you discuss data of your observation, you should first transcript your video recordings, review repeatedly and continually code as you do in discussing findings of data collected via individual and focus group interviews.

For example, observation analysis for the study done to understand the kinds of stressors originating from academic work setting, the influences of those kinds of stressors on academic staff and to know how they overcame stress at work setting can be as following:

"In the observation in International Week 2012 organized by ..., at ... on ... just as the participants stated the problem of ICT in the interviews, I witnessed the breakdown of the projection during slide show in a big auditorium at international week. A staff was presenting a documentary film by power point called `Life in Namibia`. But suddenly the projection broke down. Many young boys from ICT department came but could not fix it. So he overcame this stressor originating from the breakdown of ICT by using an alternative material for the seminar, he just came in front of audience and played the guitar and sang a folk song of Namibia. He went on playing at least 30 minutes. In another observation in International Week 2012 organized by ... at ... on ..., just as participant PDF stated: "I also think that sometimes ICT is a bit of problem of my colleagues as well. Because they don't know how to use it or when there is a small problem, they don't know how to fix it", I witnessed a staff complaining about there was

no computer in the class where she was going to give a lecture and called ICT officers to tell about and the officer came to help her, but it was funny that she did not notice that there was a computer attached just behind the monitor”

(Gunbayi, 2014: 67-68)

3.5 Discussing Findings of Data Collected via Documents

When you discuss data of documents, you should first review repeatedly and continually code as you do in discussing findings of data collected via individual interviews.

For example, document analysis for the study done to understand the kinds of stressors originating from academic work setting, the influences of those kinds of stressors on academic staff and to know how they overcame stress at work setting can be as following:

“Weekly schedules of all participants were analysed in terms of their workload and types of work in ... spring semester. Except PDB, PDD, PLB, PLD and PDF, all participants worked full time during the academic semester. PDA worked at Pre-School Education Program in Teacher Training College, PDB, PDC, PDD, PDE, PDF and PLA, PLC and PLD at Primary Education program, PLE both Primary and Pre-School programs and PLF both Primary and Secondary programs, PLB as a manager at international affairs department ... PDA coached eight students, PDB twelve, PDC nineteen, PDD and PLE twelve, and PDF fourteen, PLC five, PLD seventeen and PLF thirty. PDA visited schools for observing practical teacher training of students two days a week, PDB ,PDC and PLC one and half a day, PDD and PDF one, PLD and PLE half a day, PLF one and also PLA one but for checking practice in schools and dealing with the problems. PDA and PLD taught courses for six hours a week, PDB did not teach in autumn term, PDC eleven hours, PDD eight hours, PDF three, PLC four, PLE fourteen and PLF ten. PDA attended meetings one and half a day a week, PLE one day, PDB, PDC, PLC and PLD half a day, PDE and PLA four and half a day and PDF and PLB two days...”

(Gunbayi, 2014: 68).

3.6 Tools, Equipment, Supplies, and Materials

The following tools, equipment, supplies, and materials are needed:

Table 10: Tools, Equipment, Supplies, and Materials for Enabling Objective #2

-
- | | |
|---|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Voice recorder,• Camera,• Computers,• Laptop Software• Textbooks,• Articles,• Databases in related field, | <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Quantitative analysis software (SPSS, Lisrel),• Qualitative Analysis Software (NVIVO),• Plagiarism Detection Software,• Microsoft Office ,• Internet,• Printer/scanner/fax. |
|---|--|
-

3.7 Worker Behaviors

Academician behaviors play a key role in analyzing qualitative research data. The behaviors important to your success in completing this task are:

Table 11: Worker Behaviors for Enabling Objective #2

<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Careful• Detail oriented• Hard working• Creative• Innovative	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Self-motivated• Flexible• Trustworthy• Adaptable• Ethical Reliable
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3.8 Self Check

Directions: Check your knowledge of practicing analysing qualitative data by responding to the following questions. For True/False questions, circle “True” if the statement is correct and circle “False” if the statement is incorrect. For multiple choice questions, select the response that is most correct. For short answer questions, write a brief response to the question. Check your answers with those on the Self-Check Model Answers page that follows.

Table 12: Self Check Model Questions for Enabling Objective #2

<p>1. Qualitative data analysis computer program called NVIVO actually perform the analysis</p> <p>True False</p>	
<p>2. Qualitative data analysis includes three steps: thematic analysis, descriptive analysis and content analysis.</p> <p>True False</p>	
<p>3. During data analysis, the data should be organized categorically and chronically, reviewed repeatedly and continually coded</p> <p>True False</p>	
<p>4. You can show the result of.....analysis in frequencies, percentages and graphics.</p> <p>a. Thematic Analysis b. Descriptive Analysis c. Content analysis d. Kappa</p>	
<p>5. Why should we use qualitative data software to analyze qualitative data? Give your reasons</p>	

3.9 Self-Check Model Answers

Directions: Compare your answers to the Self-Check with the Model Answers provided below.

Table 13: Self-Check Model Answers for Enabling Objective #2

1. False	The title of the manuscript must necessarily reflect the whole manuscript otherwise it does not make a sense.
2. True	
3. True	
4. A	Thematic Analysis
5. Model Answer	A qualitative data analysis programs supports the researcher doing the analysis by organizing data and recodes and nodes etc. and it provides a workspace and tools to enable researchers to easily work through their information. With purpose built tools for classifying, sorting and arranging information, qualitative research software gives researchers more time to analyse their materials, identify themes, glean insight and develop meaningful conclusions.

Level of Performance: Your responses to the items on the Self-Check should match the Self-Check Model Answers. If you missed some points or have questions, review the Information Sheet, or if necessary, consult with your mentor.

3.10 Practice Exercise

You should follow directions below for Practice Exercise for Enabling Objective #2:

- Conduct the activities listed below using the following checklist.
- Continue practicing until you achieve a Yes rating for every item on the checklist provided in this Practice Exercise.
- Ask your co-worker to check your practice using the checklist below.

Table 14: Practice Exercise for Enabling Objective #2

Analyzing Qualitative Data Actions	Level of Performance		
	Yes	With Help	No
When analyzing qualitative data, the learner...			
1. Organized data categorically and chronically,			
2. Reviewed repeatedly			
3. Continually coded			
4. Analyzed findings using main topics according to how data are collected via individual interviews			
5. Analyzed findings using main topics according to how data are collected via focus group interviews			
6. Analyzed findings using main topics according to how data are collected via observations			
7. Analyzed findings using main topics according to how data are collected via documents			

Level of Performance: When you are finished with this Practice Exercise, you should be able to comfortably discuss and perform any of the actions included in it. Your ratings on the checklist for this Practice Exercise should be Yes for all items. If you received With Help or No ratings for any items, review your performance with your mentor.

4. Discussing and Concluding Results

As seen in Learning Experience #3, you should follow the steps of learning activities by taking care of special instructions in Practice Discussing and Concluding Results.

Table 15: Learning Experience #3

Enabling Objective #3: Practice Discussing and Concluding Results	
Learning Activities	Special Instructions
Read the Information Sheet titled “Practice Discussing and Concluding Results” on 4.1, 4.2, 4.3 and 4.4, 4.5 and 4.6.	
Watch the discussing and concluding results of Qualitative data analysis video and identify the important messages to convey about your academic position at university when developing a qualitative research manuscript.	https://www.qsrinternational.com/nvivo/nvivo-12-tutorial-windows/00-let-s-get-started
Discuss with the instructor expert in qualitative research at your faculty how he or she uses to discuss and conclude a qualitative data . What would you have to do differently?	Ask your mentor to suggest a co-researcher who can observe and help you with your practice sessions and the Practice Checklist.
Demonstrate your knowledge of discussing and concluding results of Qualitative data by completing the Self-Check Model Questions on 4.7.	
Check your answers against the Self-Check Model Answers on 4.8.	
Practice Discussing and Concluding Results while the academic staff expert in qualitative research observes and offers help as needed. Ask the academic staff expert in qualitative research to use the checklist titled “Practice Discussing and Concluding Results ”on 4.9 to assess your progress.	
Arrange to complete this Learning Guide titled “Developing A Qualitative Research Manuscript” by asking your mentor to evaluate your performance using the criteria in the Performance Test on 5, 5.1.	

4.1 Discussing Findings

You should decide which findings to take priority and discuss analytically by focusing on what findings really contribute to the phenomena of your research in the studies done so far and what are the similarities and difference between your research and studies done so far so that you can contribute to relevant research literature.

For example analytical discussion on what findings really contribute to the phenomena of the research in the study called Academic Staff's Perceptions on Stressors Originating From Interpersonal Relations At Work Setting: A Case Study (Gunbayi, 2009) and done to analyse what stressors originating from colleague-colleague interpersonal relations in academic setting are and what academic staffs' perception on stress as a result of stressors originating from colleague-colleague interpersonal relations in academic setting – informal and formal relations with colleagues- are and what their views are in overcoming those kind of stress can be seen as follows:

“Work stress may have both positive and negative effects. Research on work stress done so far tends to focus on its negative effects (Allen, 1990; Hellriegel et al., 1995). However, PG was against the assumption that work stress is necessarily a bad thing: ‘If stress is everything which disturbs your normal balance, there must be some level of stress. With your questions, I get the assumption that stress is negative. Well I don’t necessarily agree with this assumption.... to teach well, you need a little bit stress. If you are completely relaxed, you can’t teach well and it is also necessary for a good performance.’ As it can be understood what P.G. said, some forms of stress can energize people, not necessarily bad for people and people need an optimum level of stress and eustress. Additionally, if people are completely relaxed, they cannot do their job well and so stress is also necessary for a good performance.”

(Gunbayi, 2009: 58)

4.2 Summarizing and Concluding

You should decide what significant conclusion to write focusing on significant conclusion consistent with your findings so that readers who have a quick look to review literature may have no idea on your research and can cite your research.

For example summarizing and concluding of the research done to analyze what stressors originating from colleague-colleague inter personal relations in academic setting are and what academic staffs' perception on stress as a result of stressors originating from colleague-colleague interpersonal relations in academic setting – informal and formal relations with colleagues- are and what their views are in overcoming those kind of stress can be seen as follows:

“In faculties, there can be formal relations such as meeting with manager, programme and department meetings, union meetings, one to one formal meetings, committees, teaching courses, exam boards, conferences, supervision meetings, formal notifications and petition. As a result of those formal relations, there can be stressors such as badly

planned meetings, being interrupted, pressure on time, difficulty to reach a decision, workload, lack of administrative support, dominating, talking too much, conflict in arguments, not to know what to talk about, imbalance between responsibility and power, being professional, individualization, institutionalization and unpredictability. ... To sum up, there are intensive and various kinds of colleague- colleague interpersonal formal and informal relations in academic setting and those relations might have negative effects on academic staff as well as positive effects to some extent in universities. Thus, both academic staff and managers had better be aware of the stressors which are likely to affect academic work life negatively and positively in universities in order to create an academic setting where friendly relations in interpersonal relations should exist and thus where colleagues work effectively."

(Gunbayi, 2009: 59).

4.3 Reporting Recommendations

You should decide what recommendations to put forward both for practitioners and researchers by suggesting attractive and innovative recommendations consistent with your findings so that your published manuscript may influence prospective researchers, you can lead them and you can be a familiar scientist in your own field.

For example reporting recommendations of the research done to analyze what stressors originating from colleague-colleague interpersonal relations in academic setting are and what academic staffs' perception on stress as a result of stressors originating from colleague-colleague interpersonal relations in academic setting – informal and formal relations with colleagues- are and what their views are in overcoming those kind of stress can be seen as follows:

"These findings have important implications for the professional work life of academic staff. This study analyses the perceptions and past experiences of academic staff on work stressors originating from formal and informal interpersonal relations and those analysis are likely to enrich knowledge in understanding how stress influences colleagues' performance negatively and positively and identifying where unhealthy and healthy stress exists in academic setting. In addition, this study suggests important implications about what can be done to help academic staff to overcome or reduce the effects of negative stressors originating from interpersonal relations in academic setting as academic staff themselves expressed their views and suggested solutions on how to overcome stress. One another implication the study has is that stress is not necessarily bad and a negative thing. In a sense, stress to some extent is necessary to activate and energize people and for a good performance."

(Gunbayi, 2009: 58-59).

4.4 Writing References and Adding Appendices

You are supposed to decide how to organize references (number or alphabetical order by taking care of author guidance of the journal you will submit for publication and its

manuscript writing guidelines. Otherwise, the manuscript can be rejected or sent you back for redesigning by the reviewers and editors of a journal.

For example, an organization and writing of references of the article called The Effect of Nonformal Learning on The Disabled People and Educators: A Case Study (Vezne and Gunbayi, 2018) according guidelines of the journal European Journal of Education Studies can be seen as follows:

Table 16: A Sample of Writing of References

References

1. Clarijs, R. (Ed.). (2005). *Non-formal and informal education in Europe*. Prague: EAICY.
2. Cohen, L., Mannion, L. and Morrison, K. (2007). *Research methods in education*. UK: Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group.
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6. Hromatko, I. (2008). Stigma – teatar kao mjesto prevladavanja stigmatizacije. *Sociologija i prostor : časopis za istraživanje prostornoga i sociokulturnog razvoja*, 77-100.
7. Hromatko, I., Vezne, R. & Gunbayi, I. (2016). The opinions of the disabled participants and educators on Erasmus+ KA2 project: A case study. *International Journal on New Trends in Education and Their Implications*, 94-107.
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9. La Belle, T.J. (1982). Formal, nonformal and informal education: A holistic perspective on lifelong learning. *International Review of Education*. 28(2), 159-175.
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Source: Vezne and Gunbayi (2018)

You should also add appendices such as consent form, ethical committee approval and formal permission got from institutions. An example of consent form can be seen as follows:

Table 17: A sample of Consent Form

Consent Form

, 2018

My signature on this form indicates that I agree to participate in a study byon..... This will include face-to-face interviews, focus group interviews and monthly observations of daily activities and monthly analysis of academic staff's schedule and document (meetings, course minutes, exam papers, and extra works).In the event that I and the researcher decide that a second interview is not necessary there will be one interview. It also shows that I understand the following:

- I am volunteer and can withdraw at any time from the study.
 - There is no risk of physical or psychological harm.
 - The information I give will be strictly confidential and all the data will be collected and analysed by the researcher and will be securely at Akdeniz University for seven years at which time it will be destroyed.
 - I will receive a summary of the study upon request.
 - I am giving permission to the researcher for the research and its results being published.
- I, , agree to participate in the interviews.

 Signature of the Participant

 Date

Source: Adapted from Gunbayi I. (2011). Perceptions on School Management: A Case Study with Metaphorical Analysis", International Online Journal of Educational Sciences, 3, 2, 541-561.

4.5 Tools, Equipment, Supplies, and Materials

The following tools, equipment, supplies, and materials are needed to discussing and concluding results

Table 18: Tools, Equipment, Supplies, and Materials for Enabling Objective #3

- | | |
|---|---|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Computers • Laptop Software • Textbooks • Articles • Databases in related field | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quantitative analysis software (SPSS, Lisrel) • Plagiarism Detection Software • Microsoft Office • Internet • Printer/scanner/fax |
|---|---|

4.6 Worker Behaviors

Worker behaviors play a key role in discussing and concluding results. The behaviors important to your success in completing this task are:

Table 19: Worker Behaviors for Enabling Objective #3

- | | |
|--|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proactive • Leader • Open-minded • Creative • Innovative | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assertive • Flexible • Trustworthy • Adaptable • Objective |
|--|--|

4.7 Self Check

Directions: Check your knowledge of discussing and concluding results of a qualitative data by responding to the following questions. For True/False questions, circle “True” if the statement is correct and circle “False” if the statement is incorrect. For multiple choice questions, select the response that is most correct. For short answer questions, write a brief response to the question. Check your answers with those on the Self-Check Model Answers page that follows.

Table 20: Self Check Model Questions for Enabling Objective #3

1. You should decide which findings to take priority and discuss analytically by focusing on what findings really contribute to the phenomena of your research in the studies done so far.

True
False

2. You necessarily write significant conclusion focusing on significant conclusion consistent with your findings

True
False

3. The recommendations you put forwarded should be attractive and innovative consistent with your findings

True
False

4. How should you organize references? Why?

5. Why should you decide what recommendations to put forward both for practitioners and researchers by suggesting attractive and innovative recommendations consistent with your findings? Give your reasons

4.8 Self Check Model Answers

Directions: Compare your answers to the Self-Check with the Model Answers provided below.

Table 21: Self Check Model Answers for Enabling Objective #3

- | | | |
|----|--------------|---|
| 1. | True | |
| 2. | False | Readers who has a quick look to review literature may not have no idea on your research and do not cite your research. |
| 3. | True | |
| 4. | Model Answer | You are supposed to organize references in number or alphabetical order by taking care of author guidance of the journal you will submit for publication and its manuscript writing guidelines. Otherwise, the manuscript can be rejected or sent you back for redesigning by the reviewers and editors of a journal. |
| 5. | Model | As a scientist your published manuscript may influence prospective researchers so you |

can lead them and you can be a familiar scientist in your own field

Answer

Level of Performance: Your responses to the items on the Self-Check should match the Self-Check Model Answers. If you missed some points or have questions, review the Information Sheet, or if necessary, consult with your mentor.

4.9 Practice Test

You should follow the following directions for Practice Exercise for Enabling Objective #3:

- Conduct the activities listed below using the following checklist.
- Continue practicing until you achieve a Yes rating for every item on the checklist provided in this Practice Exercise.
- Ask your co-worker to check your practice using the checklist below.

Table 22: Practice Test for Enabling Objective #3

Discussing and Concluding Results			
Actions	Level of Performance		
	Yes	With Help	No
When discussing and concluding results of a qualitative data, the learner...			
1. Discussed findings using main topics according to findings of data collected via individual interviews, focus group reviews , observations and documents			
2. Outlined why this study is done and implications both for practitioners and researchers			
3. Reported recommendations by outlined implications both for practitioners and rescuers			
4. Ordered references systematically and consistently			
5. Kept appendices for outer reliability			

Level of Performance: When you are finished with this Practice Exercise, you should be able to comfortably discuss and perform any of the actions included in it. Your ratings on the checklist for this Practice Exercise should be Yes for all items. If you received With Help or No ratings for any items, review your performance with your mentor. After this, ask your mentor to help you practice your skills further.

5. Performance Test

You are to perform the task for developing a qualitative research manuscript as required. Your instructor will evaluate your performance using the criteria in Performance Test and Performance Standards in Table 23 and Table 24 below.

Table 23: Performance Test for Developing a Qualitative Research Manuscript

Learner's Name:	Date	
Competency: Develop a Qualitative Research Manuscript	Test Attempt 1 st 2 nd 3 rd	
Mentor's Signature/Approval	Overall Evaluation	
Directions: Your instructor will provide you one or more opportunities to develop a qualitative research manuscript. You are to perform the actions needed to deal with the situation that meets your academic requirements and research ethical practices. Your instructor will evaluate your performance using the criteria listed below.	Level	Performance Levels
	Achieved	4 – Can perform this skill without supervision and with initiative and adaptability to problem situations.
		3 – Can perform this skill satisfactorily without assistance or supervision
		2 – Can perform this skill satisfactorily, but requires some assistance and/or supervision.
		1 – Can perform parts of this skill satisfactorily, but requires considerable assistance and/or supervision.
Mentor will initial level achieved.		

5.1 Performance Standards

After performing the task for developing a qualitative research manuscript, you should fill in performance standards. In case any item receive a NO response, you should consult with your instructor to determine what additional activities you need to achieve competency in the weak area(s) in developing a qualitative research manuscript.

Table 24: Performance Standards for Developing a Qualitative Research Manuscript

For acceptable achievement, all items should receive a "Yes" or "N/A" response.	Yes	No	N/A
When developing a qualitative research manuscript, the learner...			
1. Defined the research problem clearly,			
a. Tied to the relevant literature,			
b. Up to date,			
c. Completed with literature review with appropriate references			
2. Determined research questions appropriate with research aim			
3. Selected qualitative design consistent with the aim of the research			
4. Explained sampling methodology, chose correct sampling size			
5. Explained data collection method through semi-structured individual			
a. Focus group interviews			
b. Organized observations			
c. Collected documents			
6. Followed steps to ensure reliability and validity of the study			

7. Accurately reported ethical procedures (e.g. Avoided plagiarism, guaranteed anonymity of the participants, obtained participants' written consent)

8. Organized data categorically and chronically,

a. Reviewed repeatedly

b. Continually coded

9. Analyzed findings using main topics according to data collected via:

a. Individual interviews

b. Focus group interviews

c. Observations

d. Documents.

10. Discussed findings using main topics according to data collected via:

a. Individual interviews

b. Focus group interviews

c. Observations

d. Documents.

11. Outlined why this study is done and implications both for practitioners and researchers

12. Reported recommendations by outlined implications both for practitioners and rescuers

13. Ordered references systematically and consistently

a. Kept appendices for outer reliability

Level of Performance: All items must receive a YES or NA response. If any items receive a NO response, consult with your mentor to determine what additional activities you need to achieve competency in the weak area(s).

6. Conclusion

In this study a learning package which provides the necessary knowledge and attitudinal information, and practice opportunities to develop a qualitative research manuscript based on SCID - systematic curriculum and instructional development- (Norton and Moser, 2013) is presented so that the learner would know why as well as when and how to perform the task of developing a qualitative research manuscript correctly.

In this learning guide, the most complex concepts, skills, and/or attitudes are made easy for every learner to understand, accept, and perform in developing a qualitative research manuscript. This learning guide suggests basic steps in developing a qualitative research manuscript for both academic staff and master/doctoral students in social sciences to follow. As the learner will self-practice the learning package he or she will understand to perform the task of developing a qualitative research manuscript effectively.

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Ilhan Gunbayi
DEVELOPING A QUALITATIVE RESEARCH MANUSCRIPT BASED
ON SYSTEMATIC CURRICULUM AND INSTRUCTIONAL DEVELOPMENT

Appendix 1: Duty/Task: Report A Qualitative Research Manuscript

STEPS (Required to Perform the Task)	PERFORMANCE STANDARDS (Observable & Measurable Criteria)	TOOLS, EQUIPMENT, SUPPLIES & MATERIALS (Needed)	REQUIRED KNOWLEDGE AND SKILLS (Math, Science, & Language)	SAFETY (Concerns)
1 Determine the title of the manuscript	1 Determined title appropriate with the manuscript	1 Reference books, articles, dissertations	1 Master / PhD degree in the related field	1 N/A
2 Write the abstract and key words	2 Completed abstract that reflected the content accurately	2 Database searching engine	2 Decision Making,	2 N/A
3 Review the literature	3 Defined the research problem clearly, tied to the relevant literature, up to date, completed with literature review with appropriate references	3 Text books, articles, dissertations	3 Knowledge of research problem in theory and philosophy of social sciences (the paradigm on which the method of the research is based),	3 Avoid palagrism
4 Explain the research aim and write research questions	4 Determined research questions appropriate with research aim	4 Text books, articles, dissertations related to research aim and questions	4 Knowledge of how to state main and sub research questions	4 N/A
5 Explain what qualitative design chosen	5 Selected qualitative design consistent with the aim of the research	5 Reference books on qualitative research methods	5 Knowledge of qualitative research methodology,	5 N/A
6 Explain sampling methods and techniques	6 Explained sampling methodology, chose correct sampling size	6 Reference books on research sampling methods	6 Knowledge of sampling methods and techniques for a research,	6 N/A
7 Explain data collection methods and techniques	7 Explained data collection method through semi-structured individual and focus group interviews, organized observations and collected documents	7 Reference books on qualitative research methods, Voice recorder, Camera, Computers, Laptop, Software	7 Knowledge of using voice recorder and video Verbatim transcript,	7 Ensure personal safety when travelling and at the research venue and ensure that someone you trust knows where to go for data collection
8 Explain reliability and validity of the research	8 Followed steps to ensure reliability and validity of the study	8 Reference books on research validity and reliability, SPSS software	8 Knowledge of how to supply reliability and validity of the research	8 Guarantee anonymity of the participants, obtain participants' written consent
9 Report ethical process	9 Accurately reported ethical procedures (e.g. Avoided plagiarism, guaranteed anonymity of the participants, obtained participants' written consent)	9 Ethical regulations by the committee of the intuitions you worked for, Plagiarism Detection Software	9 Using Plagiarism Detection Software to avoid plagiarism, preparing consent form for individual and focus group interviews	9 Keep data securely until destroyed
10 Analyze the data	10 Organized data categorically and chronically, reviewed repeatedly and continually coded	10 Reference books on qualitative research methods, transcripts, Nvivo qualitative software	10 Knowledge of preparing semi-structured interview forms, observation forms and documents related to research topic, collecting and analyzing real life documents	10 N/A
11 Discuss the findings	11 Discussed findings using main topics according to how data are collected: individual interviews, focus group interviews, observations and documents.	11 Transcripts, observation notes and documents	11 Knowledge of using ICT (word, excel, adobe), using Data Analysis Software(quantitative or qualitative NVIVO, SPSS) Analytical thinking, critical thinking	11
12 Summarize and conclude	12 Outlined why this study is done and implications both for practitioners and researchers	12 The results of whole manuscript	12 Analytical thinking, critical thinking	12 N/A
13 Report recommendations	13 Reported recommendations by outlined implications both for practitioners and rescuers	13 The results of whole manuscript	13 Doing research with new ideas, taking charge of his or her ideas	13 N/A
14 Write references and add appendices	14 Ordered references systematically and consistently and kept appendices for outer reliability	14 Reference books, articles, dissertations and forms	14 Consistent and well organized	14 N/A

Ilhan Gunbayi
DEVELOPING A QUALITATIVE RESEARCH MANUSCRIPT BASED
ON SYSTEMATIC CURRICULUM AND INSTRUCTIONAL DEVELOPMENT

Appendix 2: Duty/Task: Report A Qualitative Research Manuscript (Con't.)

WORKER BEHAVIORS (Important to Worker Success)	DECISIONS (Identify Decisions that Must be Made by the Worker)	CUES (Identify the Data Needed for Making Correct Decisions)	ERRORS (Indicate What May Result if Incorrect Decisions are Made)
1 Expert and professional	1 What is the correct and comprehensive title for the research?	1 Research aim	1 The title does not reflect the whole manuscript and does not make a sense
2 Goal driven	2 What and how many key words should I use to reflect the entire research?	2 Search data bases of research field	2 Key words do not reflect the whole manuscript and does not make a sense
3 Hard working, patient, dedicated to finish long-term projects, self-motivated	3 What reference books, articles, dissertations should I Review? What scientific search engines should I use?	3 Review data bases of research field related to your research aim carefully to contribute the research field	3 Literature does not support your research aim and research questions? Readers do not understand why you do this research and what contribution you do to research field
4 Detail oriented, flexible, goal driven	4 What and how many research questions should I write to reach the aim of the research?	4 Experience, review the literature related to research topic	4 The data you collected and your findings may not answer the research questions and keep you away from the research aim
5 Flexible	5 Which qualitative design should I choose? Why?	5 Experience and reference book suggestions of qualitative research methods	5 the design you choose does not comply with your research aim and you may mislead readers to do study
6 Proactive	6 Which sampling methods and techniques should I choose? Why?	6 Experience and reference book suggestions of qualitative purposive sampling method and techniques	6 The data you collected from the sampling do not support your aim and may mislead you
7 Cautious, punctual, good listener	7 How should I collect data? What materials should I use to collect data? How should I ensure my personal safety?	7 Experience, focus on the participants' thinking, supply triangulation	7 You lose your objectivity and your biases may mislead you
8 Trustworthy, professional, careful	8 What should I do to support reliability and validity of the research?	8 Do pilot study for reliability and validity of the study	8 Your manuscript submitted to a journal can be rejected due to poor reliability and validity
9 Ethical Reliable, safety-oriented	9 What steps should I follow to conform to the ethics committee of social science researches?	9 Keep up with the steps in the ethical regulations form of the ethical committee and get ethical approval before doing your research	9 Bad reputation and you do your research in vain
10 Detail oriented, open-minded	10 How should I code main themes and sub themes? Which qualitative analysis (thematic, descriptive, content) should I use?	10 Focus on participant views in transcript, participant observation notes and documents	10 You lose ideographic peculiarity of qualitative data
11 Accurate and objective	11 Which findings should I take priority and discuss analytically?	11 Focus on what findings really contribute to the phenomena your research in the studies done so far and what are the similarities and difference between your research and studies done so far	11 You cannot contribute to relevant research literature
12 Open minded	12 What significant conclusion should I write?	12 Focus on significant conclusion consistent with your findings?	12 Readers who has a quick look to review literature may have no idea on your research and do not cite your research
13 Adaptable	13 What recommendations should I put forward both for practitioners and researchers?	13 Suggest attractive and innovative recommendations consistent with your findings	13 Your published manuscript may not influence prospective researchers and you cannot lead them and you cannot be a familiar scientist in your own field
14 Accurate and careful	14 How should I organize references (number or alphabetical order)? Which journal should I submit my manuscript?	14 Take care of author guidance of the journal you will submit for publication and its manuscript writing guidelines	14 Rejection of the manuscript by the reviewers and editors of a journal

Source: Duty/Task: Report a Qualitative Research Manuscript was developed by author Gunbayi based on DACUM and SCID trainings (Norton and Moser, 2007; Norton and Moser, 2013) on 14-18 September 2017 and July 23-27 2018 at CETE in Ohio State University.

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